

STUDY OF VERBS AND VERBAL CATEGORIES IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: *Tense, voice, mood and facial number are the features that make up the verb as a language unit. Each verb can have all or a part of the listed properties. To this date, theoretical studies in the English language have revealed the types of action and the state of the meaning of the verb, and also studied the verb-specific features, such as tense, facial-number, mood, voice. The article discusses the main features and types of meaning of the verb and the characteristics of these categories.*

Key words: *verb, action, state, tense, mood, voice, facial number, grammatical category.*

In most languages, the verb is a weighty grammatical unit of language that makes up a large proportion of the lexical layer. For this reason, linguists around the world believe that a detailed study of the grammatical and semantic features of the verb serves to understand the general nature and mechanisms of language. In particular, the grammatical peculiarities and semantic features of English verbs were first studied in detail by scholars such as B.K. Malinovsky, F.R. Palmer, R.H. Roberts, M.Khallidey, representatives of the London School of Linguistics . By summarizing the work of these and other scholars of the London School of Linguistics, English verbs can be divided into two groups according to their meaning. The first type of meaning is action - action verbs (dynamic verbs) are one of the basic, hierarchical lexical groups of English lexicon that occupy one of the highest points. Verbs belonging to this group can mean the physical movement of a person, natural phenomena, the physiological movement of living things, automated movement. State verbs are the second type. In English linguistics, words denoting processes such as subject characteristics, attitudes, emotions, and mental activity are interpreted as stative verbs. For example, action is understood from the meaning of verbs such as: to cross, to punch, to crawl, to flow, to squat, to crouch.

Lexemes such as *to possess, to include, to stare, to observe, to conduct*, mean the state. But English verbs cannot be limited to just these two groups. Because in English, the verb has three meanings - there is also a large group of auxiliary verbs

in the verbs, which are mainly divided into action and state. The type of so-called auxiliary, conjunctive verbs, or auxiliary verbs includes lexical-grammatical units whose grammatical function is superior to the lexical meaning, which performs mainly the grammatical function in speech. For example, modal verbs, auxiliary verbs that help in the construction of tense constructions, and the verb to be (to be) are among them. The third group of verbs is not a group separated by the feature of pure meaning, because the lexical meaning of these verbs is very narrow, and has the property of changing depending on the main meaning of the verbs of state or action. But when they move into speech, they mean functional meanings such as time, proportion, inclination, and person-number. Which of their grammatical functions they perform varies depending on where they are used.

In English linguistics, state and action verbs are distinguished by their polysemantic character, while the third group of connected verbs is described as having a highly polyfunctional nature. Verbs in English have a polysemantic character - the second group of verbs that express action or state, called pure verbs, has been proven to have multiple meanings. The ambiguity of action verbs is not lexical polysemy, but lexical-grammatical polysemy. The group of action verbs is also divided into several meanings in its structure. In English, action verbs can be classified into meanings such as mechanical movement, natural movement, and human line movement. But such a classification does not occur in most works that study the semantic properties of action verbs. The semantic types of case verbs are described in detail by English linguists - summarizing the research, it can be said that case verbs in English are divided into six main types according to their lexical meaning.

1. Verbs of verbal activity: *to say, to claim, to utter, to pronounce, to spell, to joke, to speak, to argue, to articulate, to beg, to convey, to drawl, to falter, to grumble, to laud, to mutter, to narrate, to nag*

2. Emotional verbs: *to sense, to feel, to seem, to delight, to enjoy, to hear, to love, to despise, to hate, to worry, to fear, to adore, to desire, to see, to smell, to taste, to look*

3. Mental state verbs: *to trust, to calm, to believe, to suffer, to struggle, to hesitate, to rely, to suspect, to loath, to appreciate, to ignore, to concern, to resist, to predict*

4. Verbs of mental activity: *to comprehend, to apprehend, to realize, to deduce, to recall, to invent, to suspect, to wonder, to agree, to view, to detect, to refer, to regard, to recall*

5. Static verbs: *to stumble, to locate, to stay, to inhabit, to suspend, to reprieve, to stand, to standstill, to postpone, to wait, to await, to stare, to remain, to hang, to linger*

6. Verbs of belonging / possession: *to possess, to own, to have, to consist, to include, to contain, to cover, to belong, to hold, to keep, to lack, to be, to depend, to involve*

Each meaning group contains from a few to hundreds or thousands of case verbs, some conditional verbs being able to convey multiple meanings. This suggests that case verbs in English have a polysemantic nature. In English, when talking about the verbal polysemy of the case verb, it is appropriate to make the following point: "The choice of one of the different meanings of the verb depends on the context of the speech. A broadly meaningful unit has a semaphore out of context. But this same meaning shows a huge semantic reference, a conceptual scale, when interacting with different objects (words). Exactly one meaning is selected from this boundary. The meaning of the verb does not change depending on the context, on the contrary, the broad content narrows down to one meaning."

Among the main grammatical features of English verbs are the meanings of tense, person-number, inclination, ratio, modality. In general, these characteristics are present in verbs in almost all languages. The only reason for the differences in language structure is that these basic categories of the verb appear differently in speech. For example, in English, the tense category is distinguished by clear patterns. Past, present, and future tenses are common, and they are further subdivided into simple, continuous, completed, and continuous completed forms. Each species has its own different device - the form to be + ing means continuity, to be signified at different times to indicate whether the action continues in the past, present or future tense. The reason why we begin the analysis of tenses from this continuous form is that in English some conditional verbs, such as mood, possession / belonging, and contemplation, are not used in continuous tense. Formally this is possible. However, English linguists unanimously conclude that the use of these conditional verbs in the continuous tense does not make sense, as all conditional verbs have a static semant in their structure. This conclusion also applies to the have-been + ing construction of the continuous-completed form. Most conditional verbs are not used in the continuous and continuous-completed tense form. It follows that in English the tense covers the action verbs in full and the conditional verbs in part - and the conditional verbs are not understood in the continuous tense.

The personal pronouns of English verbs are also limited. In English, person-number differs from tense in that it covers both action and state verbs. But person-number suffixes in English are not autonomous, they are closely related to time. In some tense forms, verbs are also used in the singular - for example, in all continuous tense forms, the verb to be means the person-number meaning of the action along with the tense. But in the simple past tense, the future tense device

formed by the modal verb will, the person-number is not expressed at all in the past tense, past continuous-completed tense forms. The categories of proportion and inclination are broad, and they are not limited to the semantic type or tense form of the verb. No matter what the meaning, English verbs take any form of proportion or inclination.

In English, the rod category does not exist at all at the morphological level. There are words that have a lexical meaning of rod, but neither situational verbs nor action verbs have a gender meaning. Gender meaning is observed in English mainly in the form of nouns or adjectives. Conclusions on this and similar verbs are the findings of a study by representatives of the London School of Linguistics. Representatives of the London School of Linguistics carried out the main tasks set for them - as a result of their efforts, key word groups in English were identified, categories were divided into groups of primary meanings, and grammatical categories of lexemes belonging to independent word groups were clarified. The division of English verbs into three main types of action, state, and connection groups, as well as the identification of features such as tense, person-number, ratio, and inclination categories, are also the result of research by the London School of Linguistics. These results make it possible to study the cognitive, linguocultural, speech-pragmatic features of the verb group in English so far.

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